

Deliverable D7.5

Report on Training, Education and Networking activities

WP7

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Abbreviations

InnoWEE	I nnovative pre-fabricated components including different W aste construction materials reducing building E nergy and minimising E nvironmental impacts
CDW	C onstruction and D emolition W aste

Summary

This report aims at presenting the dissemination activities performed in the InnoWEE project in terms of events, networking, training and education programme for stakeholders.

The trainings were presented in the deliverable. It was explained what is the Training Manual document that InnoWEE Consortium will publish in different languages in October 2020.

Also, the cluster projects are presented, which together with InnoWEE focused on the reuse of CDW and implementation of the geopolymers in production of the prefabricated elements for better energy efficiency of buildings.

1 Introduction

Two of the objective of the WP7 were (i) to facilitate the links and networking between partners and external stakeholders, prospective end-users, other relevant projects and networks, and (ii) the definition of a Training Plan, development of training material, training of end-users to ensure optimal use of the system, including maintenance. This report *D7.5 Report on Training, Education and Networking activities* presents a summary of the events where InnoWEE project were disseminated and organization of the trainings workshop by InnoWEE partners.

1.1 Relation to other activities

This deliverable is related to the activities performed within the frame of *T7.2 Training and Educational program of technical results for Stakeholders* and *T7.3 Communication of project's results*. The activities were performed in accordance to the Dissemination Plan developed in the frame of *T7.1 Development of the Dissemination Plan and Networking activities* to ensure proper dissemination of the InnoWEE project's results.

1.2 Partners' contribution

For this deliverable must be acknowledged the contribution of all partners as they provided relevant information on the performed dissemination activities. The partners provided their contribution periodically in the template prepared and distributed by IZNAB.

2 InnoWEE dissemination activities

This section presents the dissemination and networking activities performed by the InnoWEE Consortium.

2.1 Events

During 4 years of its implementation the InnoWEE project was disseminated in different kinds of events and forms. In this report the focus will be put on the events where InnoWEE partners participated or which were organised by the partners. The

Table 1 presents all the collected information about the events.

During the 4 years, InnoWEE was disseminated in 72 events using different dissemination tools, like presentations, publications, posters, brochures, oral presentations, videos, and networking between the participants.

Partners started presenting the project in M4 (January 2017) and implemented:

- 15 events in the first year (M1-M12),
- 20 events in the second year (M13-M24),
- 18 events in the third year (M25-M36),
- 19 events in the fourth year (M37-M48).

It is worth mentioning that besides the COVID-19 pandemic, the InnoWEE Consortium was able to perform dissemination during 12 events in the last 9 months of the project (January 2020 – September 2020).

Table 1. All events where InnoWEE project was disseminated by the partners.

No.	Partner	Dissemination tool	Date and location	Title of the contribution	Target audience	Month
1	ZAG	Leaflets	11.01.2017 Ljubljana, Slovenia	Meeting of the European Circular Construction Alliance - adopting Circular Economy for internationalization and global competitiveness of European SMEs in Building and Construction	Experts involved in CDW	M4
2	CNR	Oral presentation	26.01.2017 Naples, Italy	Italian Geopolymer network day	Academic Community	M4
3	ZAG	Leaflets	23/24.02.2017 Ljubljana, Slovenia	COST Action CA15115 MINEA: Mining the European Anthroposphere (MINEA)	Experts involved in CDW	M5
4	ZAG	Leaflets	07/12.03.2017 Ljubljana, Slovenia	Fair Dom ("Home")	General public and professionals	M6

5	ZAG	Leaflets	31.03.2017 Ljubljana, Slovenia	23. posvetovanje slovenskih geologov	Experts involved in geology, materials	M6
6	ZAG	Leaflets, brochures and V. Ducman presented poster	19/21.04.2017 Zadar, Croatia	1st International Conference on Construction Materials for Sustainable Future	Experts involved in construction materials.	M7
7	IZNAB	Leaflets, networking	20.04.2017 Szczecin, Poland	Green buildings in the public space	Administration, investors, industry, architects, engineers	M7
8	ZAG, CNR	Presentation of project, prototypes, leaflets and brochures	11.05.2017 Ljubljana, Slovenia	International Workshop on alkali- activated materials	Experts involved in alkali-activated materials	M8
9	ZAG	Presentation	17.05.2017 Warsaw, Poland	Circular Economy in the building construction sector	Civil Engineers, architects, researchers	M8
10	IZNAB	Leaflets, networking	17.05.2017 Warsaw, Poland	How to improve strategies for research and development in Polish industry	Administration, scientists, industry, engineers,	M8
11	IZNAB	Leaflets, networking	23/24.05.2017 Poznan, Poland	Energy Future Week: GreenPOWER / EXPOPOWER 2017	Industry, engineers, administration, scientists	M8
12	RED	leaflets, brochures	22.06.2017 Padova, Italy	Aicarr conference 2017	HVAC and energy specialists	M9
13	PIETRE EDIL	Leaflets, brochures	22.06.2017 Bucharest, Romania	THE GALA OF THE ARCHITECTURE OF BUCHAREST 2017, 15th edition	Architects, engineers, energy consultants, constructors, technicians, CDW permitting authorities, CDW recycling companies / associations, technicians/craftsmen.	M9
14	CNR	Oral presentation, poster, leaflet and brochures distribution	14.07.2017 Madrid, Spain	II European Geopolymer Network	SMSs, researchers, professionals	M10
15	PIETRE EDIL	Brochures	07.09.2017 Bucharest, Romania	Dialogue with Citizens	Architects, engineers, energy consultants, constructors, technicians, CDW permitting authorities, CDW recycling companies / associations, technicians/craftsmen.	M12
16	RED	brochures, leaflets	03.10.2017 Brussels, Belgium	E2B Energy Efficient building	Energy and building construction specialists	M13

17	IZNAB	Leaflets	03.10.2017 Warsaw, Poland	How to write a good application and succeed in SME instrument?	Administration, investors, representatives of SME	M13
18	IZNAB	Leaflets	16.10.2017 Warsaw, Poland	BIM Workshop	Architects, designers, students	M13
19	PIETRE EDIL	leaflets, brochures & roll-up, speech	06/07.11.2017 Bucharest, Romania	SHARE Bucharest 2017 ROMANIAN BUILDING AWARDS 2017- SHORTLISTED- LIVING IN A DOME- THE SPHINX HOUSE SHARE Bucharest 2017	Architects, engineers, energy consultants, constructors, technicians, CDW permitting authorities, CDW recycling companies / associations, technicians/craftsmen.	M14
20	IZNAB	Leaflets	14.11.2017 Warsaw, Poland	Horizon 2020 for smart cities	Municipal authorities, investors, SMEs	M14
21	ZAG	Oral presentation - The legislation relevant to CDW recycling	15/16.11.2017 Ljubljana, Slovenia	COST Action CA15115 MINEA: Mining the European Anthroposphere (MINEA)	Experts involved in CDW	M14
22	ZAG	Oral presentation - Application talks from network members as well as new and future innovations from ZEISS	21/22.11.2017 London, United Kingdom	5th Xradia European Network Workshop	Experts involved in 3D microscopy, researchers	M14
23	IZNAB	Leaflets	30.11.2017 Warsaw, Poland	Financing Energy Efficiency in Poland, Czech Republic, Slovakia and Lithuania	Local authorities, ESCOs, SMEs, banks, research centres, universities	M14
24	PIETRE EDIL	1 Roll-up, 100 leaflets, 100 brochures	07-08.12.2017 Bucharest, Romania	SMART CITIES CONFERENCE 5th edition	Architects, engineers, energy consultants, constructors, technicians, CDW permitting authorities, CDW recycling companies / associations, technicians/craftsmen.	M15
25	IZNAB	Brochures distribution, networking	12.04.2018 Warsaw, Poland	European Innovation Council – new chance for Polish industry in Horizon 2020	Administration, government, industry, SMEs, researchers	M19

26	IZNAB	Brochures distribution, networking	24.04.2018 Warsaw, Poland	GreenPOWER / EXPOPOWER / INSTALLATIONS	Administration, industry, SMEs, researchers, manufacturers, distributors, innovators, installer	M19
27	TECNALIA	Speech	23.05.2018 Madrid, Spain	European environmental problems: how these problems are tackled with the help of the European Union - INNOWEE project	Students being between 15 and 18 years old	M20
28	IZNAB, CNR, ECO, ZAG	Presentations, speeches, brochures, poster	24.05.2018 Brussels, Belgium	ConWEEB - Converting construction waste into energy-efficient buildings	SMSs, researchers, professionals	M20
29	ZAG	Oral presentation - Development of alkali activated adhesive applicable for alkali activated panels	27.05-01.06.2018 Tomar, Portugal	Alkali Activated Materials and Geopolymers: Versatile Materials Offering High Performance and Low Emissions	Scientific audience and professionals	M20-M21
30	CNR	Poster presenting "geopolymers including CDW for application as a building material"	27.05-01.06-2018 Lisbon, Portugal	Alkali Activated Materials and Geopolymers: Versatile Materials Offering High Performance and Low Emissions	Scientific audience and professionals	M20-21
31	ZAG	Invited lecture - Alkali Activated Green Building Materials - Selected Case Studies	04-08.06.2018 Perugia, Italy	CIMTEC - International Conference on Modern Materials and Technologies	Scientist and professionals	M21
32	RED	Leaflets	04-08.06.2018 Brussels, Belgium	EU Sustainable Energy Week	Engineers, Architects, Constructors	M21
33	IZNAB	Brochures distribution, networking	07.06.2018 Warsaw, Poland	20 years of Poland in the Framework Programs of EU Research and Innovation. Horizon 2020 - the new opening	Administration, government, industry, SMEs, researchers	M21
34	AMS	Presentation, leaflets	27.06.2018 Athens, Greece	Workshop at National Technical University of Athens	Academic Community (Professors, PhD candidates)	M21

35	PIETRE EDIL	Networking, leaflet and brochure distribution	18.07.2018 Romania	Confindustria Romania – MEET AND GREET	Architects, designers, engineers, real-estate investors, other stakeholders	M22
36	IZNAB	Brochures distribution, networking, Project mentioned in Polish NCP's presentation	02.10.2018 Warsaw, Poland	Information Day for cities	Representatives of municipal authorities, investors, SMEs and research society	M25
37	RED	Leaflets	03-05.10.2018 Graz, Austria	International Sustainable Energy Conference	Engineers, Architects, Constructors	M25
38	IZNAB	Brochures distribution, networking	09.10.2018 Warsaw, Poland	2nd Conference – How to successfully create R&D strategies in Polish industry?	Representatives of Polish government, industry, SMEs and research society, consultancy and funding companies	M25
39	ZAG	Oral presentation: Durability assessment of geopolymer façade panels based on CDW Poster: Reaction to Fire Properties of Wood Waste-based Geopolymer Panels 2 articles (peer reviewed) published in the conference's proceedings	11-12.10.2018 Lisbon, Portugal	4th International Conference Progress of Recycling in the Built Environment	Experts and scientists involved in recycling of construction materials	M25
40	IZNAB	Brochures distribution, networking	16.10.2018 Warsaw, Poland	Information Day: Energy, Environment, Materials for industry and Process industry	Researchers, SMEs, partners in EU projects	M25
41	VOULA	Presentation	15.11.2018 Athens, Greece	Workshop: The InnoWEE project concept and results	Academic Community (Professors, PhD candidates), Municipality officers	M26
42	CNR	Oral presentation	30.11.2018 Faenza, Italy	3rd European Geopolymer Network	SMSs, researchers, professionals	M26

43	IZNAB	Brochures distribution, networking, Project mentioned in Polish NCP's presentation	08.01.2019 Warsaw, Poland	The new Participant Portal and what's next?	SMEs, Researchers, partners in EU projects	M28
44	PIETRE EDIL	Networking, leaflet and brochure distribution	16-17.01.2019 Brussels, Belgium	Harmoni Summit 2019	Stakeholders, associations, research institutes from 8 SPIRE sectors, standardization body	M28
45	IZNAB	Brochures distribution, networking	14.02.2019 Warsaw, Poland	What you need to know to properly calculate budget in H2020 projects	SMEs, Researchers, partners in EU projects	M29
46	IZNAB, CNR, ZAG, RED, TECNALIA	Presentations, speeches, brochures, poster	28.02.2019 Wels, Austria	TODAY's WASTE, TOMORROW MATERIAL! - Circular Economy in Construction common workshop	SMSs, researchers, professionals	M29
47	IZNAB	Brochures distribution, networking	17.04.2019 Warsaw, Poland	InfoDay - LIFE 2019	Administration, government, industry, SMEs, researchers	M31
48	PIETRE EDIL, RED	Scientific publication -1 Oral presentation Distributed brochures –30 Distributed leaflets –30	26-29.05.2019 Bucharest, Romania	CLIMA 2019	Scientists, Investors, Engineers, Architects	M32
49	IZNAB, CNR, ZAG, RED	Stand, video, poster, demonstration equipment, brochure distribution, networking	18.06.2019 Brussels, Belgium	EUSEW19 - Networking Village	SMEs, researchers, representatives of government units, other EU projects, students	M33
50	CNR	Oral presentation	19.06.2019 Lazise, Italy	Workshop: Ilprogetto Europeo InnoWEE: “From waste to Energy Efficiency”	Professionals and experts of construction and buildings fields	M33
51	CNR	Oral presentation	02.07.2019 Tokyo, Japan	QIRT - ASIA Conference 2019	Researchers, professionals	M34
52	IZNAB	Brochures distribution, networking	24-26.09.2019 Brussels, Belgium	R&I Days	Administration, government, industry, SMEs, researchers	M36
53	CNR	Stand, video, poster, demonstration equipment	27.09.2019 Padova, Italy	VenetoNight - Researchers' Night	Researchers, students - open to citizens	M36

54	TECNALIA	Presentation	07.10.2019 Bilbao, Spain	International Solid Waste Association (ISWA) World Congress	Experts involved in waste materials and circular economy	M37
55	IZNAB	Brochures distribution, networking	08.10.2019 Warsaw, Poland	Day with Horizon	Researchers, SMEs, partners in EU projects	M37
56	IZNAB	Brochures distribution, networking	09.10.2019 Warsaw, Poland	Horizon 2020 for the Circular Economy & Transforming Industry (#CETI_H2020)	Researchers, SMEs, partners in EU projects	M37
57	VOULA	Presentation	15.10.2019 Athens, Greece	Covenant of Mayors Capacity-building workshop: "The Covenant of Mayors in the era of Climate Crisis"	Municipality officers	M37
58	AMS, VOULA	Presentations, brochures, poster	16.10.2019 Athens, Greece	Workshop: InnoWEE - Innovative prefabricated components including different Waste construction materials reducing building Energy and minimising Environmental impacts	Researchers, local authorities, Greek government representatives, TV, magazines, professionals	M37
59	TECNALIA	Presentation	23-25.10.2019 Thessaloniki, Greece	SBE19: Sustainability in the built environment for climate change mitigation	Researchers, policymakers, professionals, students	M37
60	RED	Brochures, leaflets	05-08.11.2019 Rimini, Italy	Key Energy 2019 (inside ecomondo)	Companies, professional designers (engineers and architects), installers, students	M38
61	CNR, RED	Slide presentations and exhibition of produced panels	22.01.2020 Bolzano, Italy	"The European project InnoWEE: geopolymers, recycling and energy efficiency"	Professionals, companies, students	M40
62	CNR, RED	Stand with posters, samples and real-time demonstration, InnoWEE leaflets distributed	23-26.01.2020 Bolzano, Italy	KilmaHouse 2020 stand	Companies, professional designers (engineers and architects), installers, students	M40
63	VOULA	Presentation	20.02.2020 Athens, Greece	Hellenic Association of Photovoltaic Companies "Photovoltaics 2020:	Professionals, companies, organisations	M42

				The energy transformation began"		
64	ZAG	Samples of panels, brochures, posters	04-08.03.2020 Ljubljana, Slovenia		General public and professionals	M42
65	TECNALIA	Presentations	07.07.2020 Webinar, Spain	Spanish training workshop	SME, local authorities, Standards Institution and technological centres	M46
66	AMS, VOULA	Presentations, Posters, Brochures	15.07.2020 Athens, Greece	Greek training workshop	Architects, civil engineers, technicians, employees of technical services of other municipalities	M46
67	ZAG	Presentations, brochures, poster	26.08.2020 Ljubljana, Slovenia	Slovenian training workshop	Experts and engineers involved in LCA, LCCA, EPD and legislation for marketing of the innovative construction products	M47
68	PIETRE EDIL	Presentations	26.08.2020 Webinar, Romania	Romanian training workshop	Architects, Civil engineers, Designers, Local authorities	M47
69	CNR	Presentations	08.09.2020 Webinar, Italy	Italian training workshop	Architects, Civil engineers, Designers, Local authorities	M48
70	IZNAB, CNR, TECNALIA, PIETRE EDIL	Presentations	05.09.2020 Webinar, Italy	ESOF workshop of InnoWEE and Wool2Loop projects	Innovators, policy makers, journalists and educators	M48
71	RED	Presentations	29.09.2020 Webinar, Belgium	Belgian training workshop	Architects, Civil engineers, Designers, Local authorities	M48
72	ALL	Presentations	23.09.2020 Webinar	InnoWEE Final Conference	General public, Architects, Designers, Researchers, Public authorities, EC representatives, Energy engineers	M48

2.2 Clustering

To extend and facilitate the possibilities of the dissemination the InnoWEE project co-created a cluster of projects focused on re-use of CDW, production of innovative prefabricated elements for buildings and using geopolymers technology.

The first clustering was performed before M20 for the purpose of organization of the common workshop during EU GREEN WEEK. From that time the cluster consisted of 4 projects. Besides InnoWEE, there were also:

- Green INSTRUCT – Green Integrated Structural Elements for Retrofitting and New Construction of Buildings, <https://www.greeninstruct.eu/>,

- VEEP – Cost-Effective Recycling of CDW in High Added Value Energy Efficient Prefabricated Concrete Components for Massive Retrofitting of our Built Environment, <http://www.veep-project.eu/>,
- RE4 – REuse and REcycling of CDW materials and structures in energy efficient pREfabricated elements for building REfurbishment and construction, <http://www.re4.eu/home>.

For the organization of the 2nd common workshop during WSED19 in Wels (Austria) in M29, project FISSAC (Fostering Industrial Symbiosis for a Sustainable Resource Intensive Industry across the extended Construction Value Chain, <http://fissacproject.eu>) joined the cluster.

Since the beginning of 2020 InnoWEE cooperated with Wool2Loop project (Mineral wool waste back to loop with advanced sorting, pre-treatment, and alkali activation, <https://www.wool2loop.eu/en/project/>) in preparation of the common workshop for ESOF conference. The workshop was organised together in webinar form on 15th of September 2020 as it was postponed earlier due to the COVID-19 crisis.

3 Training and Education Programme

3.1 Training Manual development

Within the Task 7.2 the Consortium worked on the development of the InnoWEE training manual – the document including detailed presentation of the project, its results and achievements dedicated for public audience.

It is a document of over 70 pages, based on the content presented by leaders of WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6 to the public audience and professionals during 6 national training workshops organised by the end of the project.

The Training Manual consists of 7 main chapters:

1. **Introduction** – general presentation of the project
2. **Development of new materials and panels** – presentation of the research carried out to:
(i) identify and process Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) to obtain recycled aggregates suitable for geopolymer materials, which are the main component of InnoWEE panels; (ii) develop the geopolymer binders, suiting the pilot plant requirements and able to deliver panels with satisfactory quality; (iii) design and tune features of panels and casting/curing methods.
3. **Pilot plant and up-scaled production of new panels** – presentation of the design of the production pilot plant, up-scaling technology of the InnoWEE panels and implementation of the 6σ (six sigma) methodology by AMS to the production process.
4. **Installation, monitoring system and performance appraisal in real demo buildings** – presentation of the 4 real demo sites, what types of panels were installed in each of them. For each demo site performed installation and monitoring processes are presented.
5. **Building Energy Modelling (BEM) and virtual demo sites** – the main idea of the Building Energy Modelling is explained. The chapter presents the results of the simulation performed for each real and virtual demo site.
6. **Life Cycle Assessment** – the chapter explains the methodology of the study performed by ZAG on the environmental impacts of the InnoWEE panels and the main results of the Life Cycle Assessment.
7. **Life Cycle Cost – LCC** – presentation of the analysis of the InnoWEE product in aspect of cost considering different cost parts – production, installation, maintenance, disposal.

The Training Manual was created in English and is planned to be translated into national languages of all InnoWEE partners – Italian, Spanish, Greek, Polish, Slovenia, Romanian. The translation is almost ready in M48. When the Training Manual will be ready in all versions, it is planned to be published in M49 (October 2020) in the project website, social media (LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook groups) and ZENODO open access repository.

3.2 Training workshops

As it was planned in the dissemination plan in D7.1 developed in M6, the InnoWEE partners organised 6 national training workshops for professionals. The purpose was an introduction of the use of the new developed materials. As architects and engineers are the prescribers and technicians/craftsmen, are often the advisers of new products. The events were organised by the partners since July 2020 (M46) till September 2020 (M48). The organisation was postponed till the last months of the project due to the situation in Europe caused by COVID pandemic. To ensure

the good participation and number of audience the trainings were properly disseminated using different channels – the project website, social media, organiser partner’s website, and mails with invitations.

To monitor effectiveness of the trainings, questionnaires were developed, translated in the language where training was organised, and were distributed to the audience in paper form in Greece and Slovenia, and in electronic form using SurveyMonkey in Spain, Romania, Italy and Belgium. The summary of the organised training workshops is presented in the Table 2.

Table 2. InnoWEE training workshops

Place	Responsible	Date	Type	Target Group
Spain	TECNALIA	07.07.2020	Webinar	SME, local authorities, Standards Institution and technological centres
Greece	AMS	15.07.2020	Physical meeting (Athens)	Architects, civil engineers, technicians, employees of technical services of other municipalities
Romania	PIETRE EDIL	26.08.2020	Webinar	Architects, Civil engineers, Designers, Local authorities
Slovenia	ZAG	26.08.2020	Physical meeting (Ljubljana)	Experts and engineers involved in LCA, LCCA, EPD and legislation for marketing of the innovative construction products
Italy	CNR	08.09.2020	Webinar	Architects, Civil engineers, Designers, Local authorities
Belgium	RED	29.09.2020	Webinar	Architects, Civil engineers, Designers, Local authorities

Further short description for each of the six training workshop is presented below in sections 3.2.1-3.2.6.

3.2.1 Spanish workshop organised by TECNALIA

The Spanish training workshop was organised by TECNALIA in a webinar form on 7th of July 2020. The content presented to the audience was focused on Building Energy Modelling and results of the simulations performed by TECNALIA for real and virtual demo sites in InnoWEE.

The title of the event was *Circular economy and energy efficiency in Building Retrofitting: INNOWEE, a succeeded project*. There were 20 participants in the training and all of them were Spanish. The majority of the audience was technicians and researchers. Some of them were energy consultants and engineers.

After 1 hour session of presentation the participants had an opportunity to provide questions to the presenters. There were 5 questions form the audience:

- *Which software has been used for the modelling?*
- *Are the products market available?*
- *What’s the energy required to obtain the concrete (<1mm)?*
- *How can we get access to the presentations?*
- *Have the products been certified?*

INNOWEE National Workshop Spain

Date: July 7th, 2020

Time: 10 – 11:15 am

10:00 → **INNOWEE project presentation (ISWA)**

10:15 → **Training manuals**

- Building Energy Modeling (BEM)
 - Restructuring of Construction Sector
 - Advantages and Disadvantages
- Model Simulation Process
- Measurement and Verification (IPMVP)
- Conclusions – BEM as Decision Support Tool

10:30 → **Product Manufacturing**

- Fabrication process videos
- Thermal characteristics of the INNOWEE solutions
- Tests performed to ensure their proper behavior

10:45 → **WP4 achievements**

- Objectives of WP4
- Definition of installation/dismounting technologies and methodologies
- Cost and time evaluation of fitting procedure
- Monitoring campaign
- Modelling of energy performance of the different products
- Demo Site Results, Energy Savings and Sensitivity Analysis
- Hygrothermal Assessment
- Conclusions

11:00 → **Q&A**

Figure 1. Agenda of the training workshop of TECNALIA

Analysing the responses received through the SurveyMonkey questionnaire from the event the opinion was divided 50/50 between good and fair. Questioning about the purpose of participation, 2/3 of the responses shown that the participants wanted to learn about developments in the field of their knowledge or experience and 1/3 to exchange good practices. Regarding usefulness of the event, the majority of audience thought that the event was somehow useful for their professional work. The presentation awakening the biggest interest of the audience were the general presentation of the project and about the product manufacturing. There was 50/50 opinion about a need for similar events. A half of the audience said they would likely recommend such event for the future.

Below some screenshots from the event organiser (TECNALIA) are presented.

Figure 2. Screenshots of the event from TECNALIA.

3.2.2 Greek workshop organised by AMS and VOULA

Despite the pandemic situation, AMS and VOULA organised a physical training event in the Council Room of the Voula Municipality in Athens on 15th of July 2020. The topics were focused on the production of the geopolymer panels and implementation of the 6 σ (six sigma) methodology for more efficient and reliable production process. In parallel, participants had the opportunity to visit the Greek Demo Site, where the InnoWEE panels were installed.

Wednesday, 15th of July 2020
Training Workshop based on the InnoWEE EU project

*Location: Old city hall of Voula Muinicipality – Council Room
Afroditis 2, 16671, Vouliagmeni*

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Introduction: The basic idea of the InnoWEE project is to embed the waste from building demolition (fragmented bricks, plaster or concrete, glasses, machined wood etc.) in a geopolymer matrix to produce prefabricated insulating and radiant panels for applications in energy efficient buildings (www.innowee.eu).

In the present workshop we aim to inform the audience about the strategy that was adopted by AMS in order to produce in an upscale mode the aforementioned panels. More specifically, the audience will have the opportunity to watch a video illustrating the whole up-scale production of the panels, as well as to visit the demo site of Voula, where three types of those panels were installed. For a more specialized audience, the 6 σ methodology that was implemented during the upscale design will be also analyzed.

Hour	Topics	Speaker
09.00(CET) - 09.10	Welcome	(VVV)
09.10 - 09.30	InnoWEE project presentation	Maria Pappa (AMS)
09.30 - 09.50	Presentation of “Production definition & scale up of the InnoWEE panels”	Constantinos Tsoutis (AMS)
09.50 - 10.00	Brief presentation of the demo site in Voula	Evangelos Demetriou (VVV)
10.00 - 10.20	Q&A	All
10.20 - 10.30	Short Coffee Break	
Experts session		
10.30 - 11.00	6 σ strategy for up-scale production – implementation tools analysis & presentation	Constantinos Tsoutis (AMS)
11.00 - 11.30	Q&A	All
11.30 - 12.00	Closure of the meeting – free discussion with audience	All

The InnoWEE project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 723916.

Figure 3. Agenda of the training workshop in Athens.

The production process in the pilot plant and also the demo site in Voula were presented through oral presentation, video and visit to demo site to an audience of 20 people (architects, civil engineers, technicians, employees of technical services of other municipalities). InnoWEE brochures were also distributed to the participants.

Moreover, AMS and VOULA presented the overall concept of the InnoWEE project and the main achievements. The production process was described and also illustrated via the production video that was created by AMS. Finally, the real ETICS-like, Ventilated and Wood (internal) panels were shown to the audience in the demo site.

During the visit at the demo site in Voula Municipality, many participants asked questions about:

- how the ventilated facades function (air circulation etc.),
- how the panels (ETICS-like and ventilated) were attached to the walls (anchoring systems and techniques),
- the monitoring processes that were followed for the evaluation of the panels performance.

Below photos from the training workshop are presented.

Figure 4. Training workshop in the Council Room of Voula Municipality.

Figure 5. Workshop participants during the visit in the Greek demo site.

Resulting from the questionnaires distributed to the participants, 2/3 of them thought that it was an excellent event, and 1/3 said about the event as good. The majority (76%) of the participants said that they participated in the workshop to learn about developments in their field. The rest participated looking for the opportunity to exchange good practices. For the 25% of the audience the event was extremely useful, while the majority of the audience answered that it was very useful. Most of the participants were more interested in the presentation of production definition and scale up of the InnoWEE panels and in the visit in the demo site. Such event would be very likely or likely recommended by the audience for the future organisations. The majority of the audience was engineers, while there were some architects as well. There were also technicians and an administrative officer present during the training workshop.

3.2.3 Romanian workshop organised by PIETRE EDIL

On 26th of August 2020 PIETRE EDIL organised a web training event. During the event it was presented to the audience the installation and design of the InnoWEE panels with an economic analysis resulting in the total ownership cost for the panels. There were 22 participants in the workshop, where the majority was architects and engineers. There were also researchers, local authorities or students. Most of the participants were Romanians, while there were also 4 Italians and 1 Polish.

Over the 90% of the audience thought that the event was excellent, while for the rest it was good. Most of the people wanted to learn about the developments in their field, however there were people for whom the event was an opportunity for exchange of the good practices and networking. All of the participants considered the event as useful for them. In the audience opinion the most interesting part was presentation of the 3 types of the innovative panels. The audience would very likely of likely recommend such event for the future.

PROGRAM AND SPEAKERS

Hour 15:30

- General description of European project InnoWEE: objectives and activities;
- The innovative products - modular insulation systems, ventilated facades, radiant panels;
- Traditional versus InnoWEE panels - advantages of the innovative products.

Hour 16:00 Coffee break

Hour 16:30

- Installation and disassembly of the products;
- Costs results-Traditional versus InnoWEE panels;
- From small-scale manufacturing to industrial production;
- Conclusion.

Ore 17:00

- Round table with the speakers and interactive feedback from those present.

SPEAKERS

Legal/Financial Auditor
Fodor Elena Loredana

Architect
Leonardo Rossi

MORE INFORMATION ABOUT:

WWW.INNOWEE.EU

Coordinator: Dr.Mrs. Adriana Bernardi, CNR - ISAC.

Figure 6. Agenda of the Romanian training workshop

3.2.4 Slovenian training workshop organised by ZAG

On 26th of August 2020 ZAG organised a national training workshop in Ljubljana. The event was focused on the legislative procedures for positioning innovative construction products in the market and providing insight into the importance of LCA calculations for assessing the environmental acceptability of newly developed products. 25 people participated in the physical event. They were Slovenian researchers and engineers, experts involved in LCA, LCCA, EPD and legislation for marketing of the innovative construction products. In their opinion organisation of the event was excellent or good. For most of the participants (15) the event was an opportunity to learn about development in their field, for 5 of them it was a possibility to exchange knowledge, and for 5 to networking. All of the participants would likely or very likely recommend organisation of similar workshop in the future.

Figure 7. Samples of the InnoWEE panels were presented to the audience

Figure 8. Photos taken during ZAG’s training workshop

At the end of the event the Q&A session was organised where the participants gave a few questions to know more about the project, for example:

- Will be InnoWEE products produced industrially after the end of the project?
- Are CDW classified according to EU legislation pure enough and have constant chemical composition for further use?

From Waste to Energy Efficiency

ZAG

VABILO NA DELAVNICO

Pozicioniranje inovativnih gradbenih proizvodov na tržišče in LCA analiza

V okviru projekta [InnoWEE](#) (*Innovative pre-fabricated components including different waste construction materials reducing building energy and minimising environmental impacts*) smo konzorcijski partnerji razvili in testirali več proizvodov, ki služijo kot fasadne obloge in sevalni paneli. Pri razvoju novih inovativnih gradbenih proizvodov je pomembno poznati postopke, kako jih lahko tržimo, kje so eventualne ovire in kako k njihovi končni okoljski oceni doprinesemo z LCA analizo.

Na primeru projekta InnoWEE želimo v okviru delavnice prikazati zakonodajne postopke za pozicioniranje inovativnih gradbenih proizvodov na tržišče ter podati uvid v pomembnost LCA izračunov za oceno okoljske sprejemljivosti novo razvitih proizvodov.

KDAJ: sreda, 26. avgust 2020, od 10. do 13. ure

KJE: Zavod za gradbeništvo Slovenije (ZAG), Dimičeva ulica 12, Ljubljana

Program delavnice:

10.00- 10.10	Uvodni pozdrav in predstavitev delavnice; dr. Vilma Ducman, ZAG
10.10- 10.30	Kratka predstavitev ciljev in dosežkov projekta, Ana Frankovič, ZAG
10.30- 11.00	Zakonodajni okvir trženja inovativnih gradbenih proizvodov, dr. Vilma Ducman, ZAG
11.00 -11.20	Odmor za kavo
11.20 - 11.40	LCA/trajnostnost novo razvitih proizvodov; teoretični del, Friderik Knez, ZAG
11.40 – 12.40	Prikaz izračuna LCA za fasadne panele; praktični del, Anja Lešek / Friderik Knez, ZAG
12.40 – 13.00	Pomen razvojnih in demo pilotnih projektov pri prehodu v krožno gospodarstvo, dr. Dragica Marinič, SRIP-Krožno gospodarstvo, Štajerska gospodarska zbornica

Delavnico organiziramo v sodelovanju s SRIP Krožno gospodarstvo.

Vljudno vabljeni!

dr. Vilma Ducman, vodja slovenskih partnerjev projekta InnoWEE

Delavnica bo potekala v živo. Število mest je zaradi trenutnega stanja omejeno, zato vas prosim za čimprejšnjo prijavo oz. potrditev udeležbe na e-pošto: katja.traven@zag.si Kotizacije ni.

Projekt je financiran s strani EU programa Horizont 2020 s pogodbo št. 723916. *Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 723916.*

REPUBLIKA SLOVENIJA
MINISTRSTVO ZA GOSPODARSKI
RAZVOJ IN TEHNOLOGIJO

EVROPSKA UNIJA
EVROPSKI SKLAD ZA
REGIONALNI RAZVOJ
NALOŽBA V VAŠO PRIHODNOST

»Naložba sofinancirata Republika Slovenija in Evropska unija iz Evropskega sklada za regionalni razvoj.«

Figure 9. Agenda of the workshop organised by ZAG

3.2.5 Italian training workshop organised by CNR

On 8th of September CNR organised an Italian training workshop in form of a webinar streamed from a physical location, as shown in the photo of the event. The speakers were hosted at the meeting room of the Padova architects board (Ordine degli Architetti, Pianificatori, Paesaggisti e Conservatori della Provincia di Padova). The discussion with the audience was moderated by an architect representative of the board.

Figure 10. Photo of the Italian workshop organized by CNR.

The purpose of the event was to present the exciting journey from the conception of new materials to design, production (first in the laboratory and then on a pilot plant), installation on demonstration buildings and final verification in the field of performance of new building components. 57 Italian architects and engineers interested in building performance and energy saving participated in the training. According to the opinions from the questionnaires it was good event (more than 70%) or even excellent (near 20% of answers). 78% of the audience participated with the purpose to learn about the development in their field and 17% to exchange good practices. The majority of the audience gave an answer that the event was very useful or somewhat useful for their professional work.

PROGRAMMA	<p>Ore 14:00</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Il progetto europeo InnoWEE: obiettivi e attività per l'efficienza energetica degli edifici. » Il recupero dei rifiuti inorganici da costruzione e demolizione per la produzione di aggregati riciclati. » I geopolimeri: una soluzione a basso impatto ambientale per il recupero dei materiali di scarto. » I prodotti del progetto InnoWEE: sistemi modulari a cappotto, facciate ventilate, pannelli radianti. » La produzione e la qualificazione degli elementi modulari. <p>Ore 15:30 Coffee break</p> <p>Ore 15:45</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Le prove sperimentali di efficienza termica sui pannelli InnoWEE. » L'installazione negli edifici pilota: modellazione energetica e monitoraggio delle prestazioni. » Dalla manifattura in piccola scala alla produzione industriale » La valutazione del ciclo di vita del prodotto » Conclusioni <p>Ore 17:30</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Tavola rotonda con i relatori e feedback interattivo dei presenti 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Adriana Bernardi, CNR - ISAC » Sergio Tamburini, CNR - ICMATE » Marco Natali, CNR - ICMATE » Matteo Panizza, CNR - ICMATE » Giovanni Ferrarini, CNR - ITC » Paolo Bison, CNR - ITC » Anna Casati, Magnetti Building S.p.A. » Giulia Mezzasalma, Red S.r.l. <p>MAGGIORI INFORMAZIONI SU:</p> <p>INNOWEE.EU </p> <p>Il progetto InnoWEE (Innovative pre-fabricated components including different waste construction materials reducing building energy and minimizing environmental impacts) ha ricevuto finanziamenti dal programma di ricerca e innovazione Horizon 2020 dell'Unione europea nell'ambito dell'accordo di finanziamento n. 723916. Coordinatore: Dr.ssa Adriana Bernardi, CNR - ISAC.</p>	RELATORI
			CONTATTI

Figure 111. Agenda of the Italian workshop of CNR.

Some questions from the attendees regarded: the use of the geopolymers, especially in comparison with the current standard construction materials; the possibilities and limitations the legislation related to the CDW; the life cycle analysis.

3.2.6 Belgian training workshop organised by RED

Belgian training workshop was organised by RED in a webinar form on 29th of September 2020. The purpose was to give a presentation of all the developments and the results of the project. The Belgian Confederation of the Construction Industry hosted the webinar for its members. There were 13 formal subscriptions of which half from industrial companies active in the building construction business as shown in the table below.

Panneaux préfabriqués : une nouvelle opportunité de valorisation pour les déchets de déconstruction ?

Présentation des résultats d'un projet de recherche

Webinaire – mardi 29 septembre 2020 à 17h30

Le secteur de la construction est parmi les plus grands producteurs de déchets, tandis que près de la moitié des ressources naturelles exploitées en Europe lui sont destinées. Et si l'on pouvait utiliser une partie de ces déchets pour créer des panneaux préfabriqués qui augmentent la performance énergétique des bâtiments, tout en diminuant leur impact environnemental ? C'est l'objectif que s'est fixé le projet InnoWee, une recherche de 4 ans financée par des fonds du programme européen «Horizon 2020».

Au programme de ce webinaire, nous reviendrons sur le processus développé au sein du projet InnoWee qui permet de fabriquer des panneaux isolants et radiants à partir de déchets de construction et de démolition (inertes et bois) et des géopolymères.

Vous souhaitez en savoir plus ?

[S'INSCRIRE](#)

Sommaire du webinaire :

- Qu'est-ce qu'un polymère ?
- Quels déchets de construction et de démolition utiliser ?
- Quels panneaux peuvent être fabriqués ?
- Tests en laboratoire, production pilote et premiers essais
- Résultats et développements futurs

Orateur : Luc Pockelé – Red srl

Figure 12. Invitation for the Belgian workshop prepared by RED.

The outcome of the questionnaire was that for all participants the seminar was at least useful. The most interesting topics for the audience were the reuse of the construction and demolition wastes and the life cycle analysis of the InnoWEE products. Over 60% of the participant would probably or very probably recommend to follow the seminar in the future.

4 InnoWEE Final Conference

On the the 23rd of September 2020, IZNAB in cooperation with all InnoWEE partners organised the Final Conference of the project. Due to the COVID-19, the event was organised in online form. The purpose of the event was to present the overall project, its objectives and final results and achievements to the general public. To properly disseminate the Final Conference, a special section was added in the InnoWEE website where the main information, agenda and speakers were presented. The invitation was designed and was published in social groups of InnoWEE (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook) and was sent by partners by mails to their contact networks.

47 people registered to participate to the conference. Among them there were researchers, teachers, students, engineers, business consultants, managers, etc. from 24 countries, not only from Europe. Finally, the audience was around 30 people.

The conference consisted of 5 topic sessions moderated by Emil Lezak (IZNAB):

- Opening session with warm welcome to the audience, short general presentation of the project presented by the Coordinator – Adriana Bernardi (CNR-ISAC), and presentation of the invited speaker – Danijel Lisičić (JUB d.o.o.).
- Presentation of the innovative products – panels – in terms of laboratory tests and the panels’ development, pilot plant production and testing of the panels.
- Presentation of the InnoWEE demo sites, the installation and monitoring process of the panels with building energy modelling simulations.
- Impact assessment of the new solutions – results of the Life Cycle Assessment followed by the certification process and standardisation.
- Market impact – presented analysis of the industrialisation for the mass production of the panels, analysis of cost of production in term of the total ownership cost and presentation of the exploitation plans for InnoWEE exploitable results.

After each main session a Q&A part took place where questions from the audience were asked. People asked about challenges for the development and implementation of the new products, about their properties in terms of competitiveness with currently existing and prospering technologies. There were 3-4 questions after each session, and the answers where given to all of them by the presenters.

Figure 13. Screenshot of a few partners being presenters in the final conference.

Innovative pre-fabricated components including different Waste construction materials reducing building Energy and minimising Environmental impacts

Final Conference of the InnoWEE Project – Agenda – 23rd September 2020

Final Conference virtual access open	9:15 – 9:30
SESSION I – InnoWEE Final Conference opening	9:30
Welcome to participants by <i>Project coordinator – Adriana Bernardi (CNR-ISAC)</i> ;	9:30 – 9:35
Challenges and opportunities of construction sector in terms of SRM implementation – <i>Danijel Lisičić (JUB d.o.o.)</i>	9:35 – 9:50
Short overview of the project and presentation of the consortium – <i>Project coordinator – Adriana Bernardi (CNR-ISAC)</i>	9:50 – 10:00
SESSION II – CDW-based new materials and products	10:00
Innovative geopolymer panels, from waste to laboratory realisation – <i>Sergio Tamburini & Giovanni Ferrarini (CNR-ICMATE&ITC)</i>	10:00 – 10:25
Pilot plant and upscaled production of the new panels – <i>Constantinos Tsoutis (AMS)</i>	10:25 – 10:45
Testing of the new products – <i>Vilma Ducman (ZAG)</i>	10:45 – 11:00
Q&A	11:00 – 11:05
SESSION III – InnoWEE demonstrators	11:05
Installation, monitoring system and performance appraisal in real demo buildings – <i>Giulia Mezzasalma (RED)</i>	11:05 – 11:35
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Italian demo site • Greek demo site • Romanian demo site • Belgian demo site 	
Building Energy Modelling and virtual demo sites – <i>Beatriz Fraga (TECNALIA)</i>	11:35 – 11:50
SESSION IV – Impact assessment of the new solutions	11:50
Life Cycle Assessment – <i>Friderik Knez (ZAG)</i>	11:50 – 12:05
Certification and standards – <i>Sabina Dolenec (ZAG)</i>	12:05 – 12:15
Q&A	12:15 – 12:20
SESSION V – Market impact / Commercialization assessment	12:20
Industrialization – <i>Francesco Sonzogni (MAGNETTI)</i>	12:20 – 12:30
Total Cost of Ownership of the Product, comparison with traditional similar products – <i>Loredana Fodor (PIETRE)</i>	12:30 – 12:40
Exploitation plans – <i>Jakub Pluta (IZNAB)</i>	12:40 – 12:50
Q&A and Closing of Final Conference	12:50
Q&A	12:50 – 13:00
Closing of the Final Conference – <i>Adriana Bernardi (CNR-ISAC)</i>	13:00 – 13:05

CONTACT

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www.innowee.eu

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Figure 14. Agenda of the InnoWEE Final Conference

5 Conclusion

In the report the dissemination activities in terms of events and networking performed by the InnoWEE Consortium are presented. During the 4 years, the InnoWEE project was disseminated by the Consortium in 72 different events. The COVID-19 pandemic was a threat to the dissemination activities in the last year of the project. However, all planned events were successfully organised safely.

As it was planned from the 6th month of the project when the dissemination plan was developed, in the last year all 6 training national workshops were organised by the partners responsible. In each of them a specific part of the project achievements has been presented to the audience. By distributing the questionnaires to the audience in printed or online form it was possible to collect additional information about the audience and know their opinions about the events. The inputs can be used in the future for organisation of similar events.

The content presented was a base for creation of the Training Manual document which after translation is planned to be published online in the open access form.

In the last month, a successful Final Conference of the project was organised in online form, where the project and its final results were presented to the general audience.

Finally, all the events, although the online ones to a lesser extent, were great opportunity for networking with different audience, where the project and the results of InnoWEE were disseminated by face to face presentations.